

DATA AUGMENTATION AND AI-BASED SENTIMENT ANALYSIS OF CUSTOMER REVIEWS IN E-COMMERCE

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Abstract: *E-commerce offers many benefits to customers, including the possibility to easily find customer reviews on desired products. Customer sentiment plays a significant role in evaluating products distributed through digital platforms. This study presents a sentiment classification framework based on customer reviews collected from Amazon Handmade. A labeled dataset was constructed by categorizing each review into one of three sentiment classes: positive, negative, or neutral. Synthetic data, generated using the GPT-4 language model, were incorporated to enrich linguistic diversity and semantic variability. This augmentation strategy improved the model's ability to generalize across varied real-world expressions and writing styles, resulting in more accurate and robust sentiment classification. The average cosine similarity between original and synthetic reviews was 0.908, indicating high semantic consistency of the augmented data. Sentiment classification was performed using both rule-based and deep learning methods. Rule-based baselines, including VADER, TextBlob, and AFINN, showed limited performance, with accuracies around 60%. In contrast, a fine-tuned BERT model trained solely on real data achieved an accuracy of 83%, while the same model trained on the combined real and GPT-4-generated dataset reached 97% accuracy. These results demonstrate that augmenting real reviews with GPT-generated data significantly enhances the reliability and accuracy of sentiment predictions.*

Keywords: *E-commerce, sentiment analysis, Amazon Handmade, BERT, GPT-4, NLP, data augmentation.*